

THE REASONS WHY PEOPLE ARE LACK OF FLUENCY IN ENGLISH

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Annotation: *This article presents different reasons why learners have difficulty speaking in English and ways as well as advice how to overcome them.*

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Most children have difficulty with how to speak in English. They can not explain reasons why they are not fluent in English yet and how to fix that, and these reasons, are going to help them that they can continue their fluency journey with confidence. The first thing is that the journey to fluency is a long one, and one that people on the whole underestimate in terms of what they need to do to reach that goal, and also how long it will take them.

Firstly, they should have motivation and the desire to improve because it is important to reach the level where they are fluent.

There are some reasons that they can not learn English or improve fluency.

1. They don't have enough time to learn English during the day. This is a common one because they all have commitments and they constantly say "I am busy, I've got this to do, I can not find the time to do this". However, if they do not want to reach a high level, if they do not want that fluent level of English, then they will need to spend more time learning English. They must find the time to do this if they want to reach their goal quickly.

2. Another important reason is that they do not learn it in smart ways. It is important to make learning English a priority, which means make it one of their number one goals. They can also listen podcasts while doing other things, which is maybe what they are doing right now. They can read daily newspapers on a daily basis. It takes them about 10 minutes to read and English articles or newspapers.

3. The third reason is that they can not change their environment and it is important to change their environment during the process of learning English. It is easy to look at their calendar and the way that they spend their day, and asking themselves if they can study instead of doing something else, and if they have a strong why, a strong motivation to do this, then it will overcome the how. They need not watch TV instead, maybe they play computer games, they do other things, and if those

things are more important, that's fine. By doing this, they can make it part of their environment.

4. The fourth reason is to stop spending so much time learning grammar rules. If they spend too much time learning grammar rules, then they are not going to progress at. Knowing grammar rules can help them to understand the way that the language is structured. In order to have natural conversations in English and to understand people when they speak, they need to intuitively know grammar in a way where it feels right, and this is where they do not have to think about the rules when speaking or listening. Instead, they automatically use correct grammar, just like English speakers do, or people with a high level. They do not think about rules, but they just use it correctly because it seems right to them and spending too much time on grammar rules is taking away time that they could spend doing something more effective. And the key is this.

5. Number five is that they are too shy to practise, they are too afraid to practise speaking English.

They feel too shy to speak in English or that they are afraid of making mistakes. There are two things that overcome this for me. The first one is they should realized no one cares when they make a mistake so when they are speaking in a foreign language, no one really cares about this. So to overcome this, just know that it is okay to make mistakes. The second one is to they find somebody who they comfortable with when practicing English. They should use small talk to ease their way into conversation and ask questions, ask people questions, and then also just really know that every time they practise, it is a way for them to improve, and it is overcome those mistakes and to know that making mistakes is part of their journey.

6. Number six is they are not consistent enough. They are not consistent enough when it comes to learning English. They all go through stages where they are excited about something new. They know the feeling when they want to do is when they start

something new is to do the new exercise that they have found or to just completely spend all their time learning how to play the guitar when they get a new guitar, or spend five hours learning English because they get motivated about learning a new language, but it is important to know that motivation comes and goes and that feeling off excitement at the start usually wears off, it usually decreases, but the key is to be consistent no matter their level of motivation. Get into the habit of learning English. There is a quote from Will Durant. "We are what we repeatedly do". Excellence, then, is not an act, but a habit. If they consistently learn English, then they become somebody who can speak English. They should do the right things now on a consistent basis and create habits that they can stick to.

7. Number seven is they do not actresses that they like.

It is one of the easiest way of how to improve speaking any foreign language. Learners should take their loved musicians or actor, actress. And they should try and do the voice and the whole body and they become that character. They can do that when they are practicing speaking on their own. They probably do not want to do this when they are out and about at the shops or speaking to foreign people. But when they are having fun at home, it can be a great way to practise. By imitating favorite english speaking actor, people can improve their speaking skills.

8. Number eight is they can not adapt with English language in their whole life.

When learners use Facebook , Telegram, Instagram, WhatsApp, other social media that have a chat facility, they often send text messages. It would be great if learners go a step further. They should send an audio message rather than a written messages. People can do this if they have some friends who maybe speak English or family members. If they do this again and again, it can be quite fun to do. And the great thing about sending audio messages is that it is not like a live phone conversation, where the pressure is thereunder people have time to prepare to think about what they are going to say to record it. If they don't like it, they can delete it, record it again. So sending audio messages is a great way to develop their speaking.

Learners always pay attention such ways that how to develop their speaking skills and strategies. To speak English fluently, they should never give up practice. Practice makes perfect. Not only these ways, but also there are lots of effective ways to improve their English. If learners should do all these strategies, they will get their desire result, without any doubt.

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